

Synthesis and Characterisation of Rubidium Picrate Complexes with Noncyclic Oxocrowns

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This communication reports the conditions favouring synthesis of crystalline complexes of rubidium with noncyclic oxocrown, where the charge neutralising anion is organic in nature, viz. 2,4,6-trinitrophenolate (Pic^-). Isolation of the complexes favoured as the anion behaves self-stabilised due to delocalisation of its charge.

Results and Discussion

Authentication of the isolated solid phase was carried out employing hot stage microscopy (melting point study), infrared and nmr spectra, diffraction using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation and elemental analyses (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES.

Compd..	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	M
RbPic (1) ^a	205	37.0 (36.7)	3.8 3.4	6.8 7.1	14.01 14.54
RbPic (2) ^b	235	38.2 (38.0)	4.2 3.8	6.4 6.6	12.96 13.54

^aCrystal data : Triclinic, $a = 7.12 \pm .03$, $b = 12.38 \pm .04$, $c = 10.02 \pm .06$ Å; $\alpha = 108.7 \pm 2^\circ$, $\beta = 117.3 \pm .4^\circ$, $\gamma = 87.5 \pm .2^\circ$, vol. 392.61 Å³, $M = 587.47$, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.313$, $D_{\text{obs}} = 1.312$, $z = 1$, space group $P1$.

^bCrystal data : Triclinic $a = 8.31 \pm .04$, $b = 9.47 \pm .03$, $c = 10.5 \pm .03$ Å, $\alpha = 112.5 \pm .4^\circ$, $\beta = 102.8 \pm .3^\circ$, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.403$, $D_{\text{obs}} = 1.412$, $z = 1$, space group $P1$.

Rubidium dinitrophenolate and orthonitrophenolate failed to produce any complex with these oxocrowns. For less nucleophilic picrates, 1 : 1 complexes were obtained from 1 : 1 as well as 1 : 2 reaction mixtures of metal salt and oxocrown. Elemental analyses and ir spectral data established the newness

and homogeneity of the isolated phases. The characteristic frequencies for enol form (1660 cm^{-1}) and keto form (1720 cm^{-1}) shifted for each complex indicating the change in conformation of the ligand during complexation. The absence of peaks at 1800 and 2500 cm^{-1} indicates the absence of H-bonded interaction between hydroxyl group and picrate anion. ¹H nmr studies show that characteristic signal for $[\text{CH}_2\text{-O-CH}_2]_n$ protons shifted downfield in the complexes. These spectral changes reveal that all donor oxygen atoms in the ligand have more or less interaction with the metal ion and cation seems to become wrapped into the pseudo-cyclic cavity¹.

The structural information and results of synthetic work show that M-ligand interaction is hampered by anion in accordance with its basicity and ion-pairing ability. By stabilising anion through delocalisation of its charge, Rb-noncyclic oxocrown interaction can be favoured. The replacement of hydroxyl group of glycol by acetoacetate group increases the coordination potentialities of the noncyclic ligand² and these noncyclic oxocrowns retained³ the properties of crown ethers.

Experimental

A mixture of tetraethylene glycol (0.66 mol) and ethylacetoacetate (2 mol) was heated slowly for 3 h at 180° at atmospheric pressure. During this period ethanol (68 ml) was collected. Once ethanol ceased to distil off, distillation was continued at 20 mm leading to the collection of excess ethylacetoacetate (b.p. 80°)⁴. The brown oily residue

was nearly pure and confirmed by ir and nmr spectra: ν_{\max} (neat) 3 500 (OH), 1 740 and 1 720 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (CDCl_3) δ 2.88 (s, 6 CH_3), 3.50 (s, 4 CH_2), 4.60 (s, 4 OCH_2) and the enol at 1.97 (s, 6 CH_3) and (s, 2 vinyl-H).

1; $n = 1$

2; $n = 2$

Rubidium picrate salt (0.2 mmol) was dissolved

in isopropanol (4–5 ml) and oxocrown (0.2 to 0.4 mmol) was added to it. The reaction mixture was chilled in a refrigerator, or alternatively, evaporated slowly at room temperature to get the crystals of the complexes.

References

1. K. HIRATANI, S. AIBA and T. NAKAGAWA, *Chem Lett*, 1980, 477.
2. R. QURESHI, U. SHARMA and V. W. BHAGWAT, *Nat Acad Sci. Lett.*, 1992, **15**, 18.
3. G. D. BRESFORD and J. F. STODDART, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1980, 867.
4. R. M. KELLOG and T. J. VERBERGIN, *J Org Chem*, 1980, **45**, 2855.